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D2.2 - Standards and regulations analysis

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D2.2 Standards and regulations analysis

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial intelligence
DL	Deep Learning
DGA	Data Governance Act
EC	European Commission
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
EnMS	Energy Management System
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	GreenHouse Gas
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
ICS	International Classification for Standards
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
ML	Machine Learning
OH&S	Occupational Health and Safety
SMS	Service Management System
TC	Technical Committee
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable is the result of the work of *Task 2.2 - Analysis of Applicable Standards and Regulations*, that “*will analyse standards and Regulations that are applicable to the project and the pilots.*”, with the objective of gathering information about Standards and Regulations.

The methodology used to identify Regulations and Standards, described in chapter two, was based on research, and its analysis, in websites dedicated to the subject. In the case of the Standards, we resorted mainly to International Organization for Standardization (ISO)¹ and International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC)² and in the case of the Regulations resorted to EUR-Lex – Access to European Union law³.

Chapter three provides for a list of regulations pertinent to the scope of AI4PublicPolicy. The regulations cover three (3) thematic areas, namely, cybersecurity, data privacy & governance and artificial intelligence. In this context, both applicable legislation as well as proposed legislation are included. Taking into account the duration of AI4PublicPolicy project, regulations that are currently proposed may become applicable in the near future. Moreover, considering proposed regulations provides additional normative elements regarding the limits of AI-systems from a legal viewpoint. Note that the abovementioned regulations will be further discussed under D1.11 “Ethical and Legal Analysis Activities V1”, due under Task 1.5 “Ethical and Legal Analysis”. Chapter three, also, complements the deliverables under Work Package 9 on Ethics Requirements.

Chapter four provides a list of Standards which may be applicable to the pilots. The list of standards is divided into categories based on use cases that were defined in D2.1 that are, General Standards, Data Standards, Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility, Citizens and Business Services Optimization, Noise Management, Energy Management and Water Infrastructure planning and maintenance.

¹ <https://www.iso.org/home.html>

² <https://iec.ch/homepage>

³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu>

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI’s potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e. AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens’ participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project’s AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project’s developments. AI4PublicPolicy’s business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project’s platform.

Figure 1: AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.2 Description of WP2 Objectives

The objectives of WP2 are to:

- Specify the overall architecture for the AI4PublicPolicy platform by identifying components, their functionalities and interconnection, ensuring their coherency with the requirements and global architecture.
- Identify and track end user and technical requirements provided by the use case partners and the technical contributors of AI4PublicPolicy.

- Review the standards and regulations and identify appropriate ones that need to be monitored and followed in the project.
- Analyse the policy making processes to ensure that the outcomes of the project address and enhance/improve these processes, while reducing the bottlenecks in public administration and ensuring high quality and adoption of results.
- Define the data models of the datasets and the policy models to be utilized for the development, training and actual utilization of the AI models and algorithms of AI4PublicPolicy.
- Define the co-creation. Relevant activities will be regularly reported in D2.8, in-line with the description of the deliverable.

1.3 Purpose and Scope

AI4PublicPolicy is a data-driven project. So, understanding the data for every pilot and building correct data models are crucial for the success of the project. Each pilot will have their own domain terminology and the datasets will contain the corresponding data.

This deliverable is the result of the work of *Task 2.2 - Analysis of Applicable Standards and Regulations*, that “will analyse standards and Regulations that are applicable to the project and the pilots. It will review and analyse technical standards associated with the main technological areas of the project, including standards-based reference architectures for AI systems, machine and deep learning models, IoT, AI security and safety and more. Likewise, applicable laws and regulations will be reviewed and documented as well, including GDPR, ePrivacy and the Network Information Systems directive. The task will document the impact of each one of these standards and regulations on the AI4PublicPolicy reference architecture and technical results. The outcomes of the task will be also fed to the standardization and pre- normative activities task in WP8, as a tangible input to the standardization and pre-normative activities planning of the project.”

The goal of this document is to gather information about standards and regulations. Standards are a repeatable, harmonised, agreed, and documented way of doing something. Standards contain technical specifications or other precise criteria designed to be used consistently as a rule, guideline, or definition. Standards are an important aspect of ensuring that products and services are delivered in a harmonised and consistent way, while providing consumers and users with the confidence that whatever products and services they are using deliver to specification.

Regulations are rules made by a government or other authority in order to control the way something is done or the way people behave. “Regulation has a variety of meanings that are not reducible to a single concept. In the field of public policy, regulation refers to the promulgation of targeted rules, typically accompanied by some authoritative mechanism for monitoring and enforcing compliance. Accordingly, for a long time in the United States, for example, the study of regulation has been synonymous with the study of the independent agencies enforcing it. In political economy, it refers to the attempt of the state to steer the economy, either narrowly defined as the imposition of economic controls on the behaviour of private business or, more broadly, to include other governmental instruments, such as taxation or disclosure requirements. The two meanings share a focus on the state’s attempt to intervene in private activities.”⁴

The Standards and Regulations that are described in this document are suggestions that pilots may or may not implement, however some of these are already implemented.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

D2.2 “Standards and Regulations Analysis” is divided in 5 chapters, which are:

- The **first chapter** of the document is introductory, aiming to provide some basic information regarding the AI4PublicPolicy project, a brief description of WP2 “Specifications and Co-

⁴ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/regulation>

Creation for AI-Based Policy Management”, the purpose and scope of the deliverable, its structure and relation to other WPs and tasks.

- The **second chapter** of the document is the methodology that was used to collect the Regulations and the Standards.
- The **third chapter** of the document provides the list of Regulations.
- The **fourth chapter** provides a list of Standards.
- The **fifth chapter** is the conclusions of the document, as well as a section with useful **appendices** related to the document.

1.5 Relation to other WPs and Tasks

WP2 “Specifications and co-creation for AI-based policy management” is devoted to producing key specifications for the project’s AI-based policy making paradigm, while including the user studies and the co-creation activities. More specifically, those work package activities:

- From WP1 “Project Management and Administration” and especially T1.5 - Ethical and Legal Analysis.
- From WP2 “Specifications and co-creation for AI-based policy management” and especially T2.1 - Reference Scenarios and Use Cases.
- From WP8 “Dissemination Exploitation and Standardization” more specifically the T8.3 - Standardization and Policy Making Activities.

2 Methodology

This section describes the approach of the work carried out to identify the Regulations and Standards that are applicable to the AI4PublicPolicy pilots. Figure 2 depicts the methodology used, describing each step taken in order to finalize the list of Regulations and Standards.

Figure 2: Methodology

The process of identifying the standards and regulations was based on research and analysis and websites dedicated to the subject.

For example, in the case of Standards, some of the sites used in the search were International Organization for Standardization (ISO)⁵ and International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC)⁶. Both are organizations that prepare and publish international standards and can be easily accessed via their websites. Each standard has its own dedicated page, as depicted in Figure 3, where plenty of information can be retrieved.

The emphasis of the standards was based on the analyses of Pilots' User Stories, (see D2.1 for more detail of these categories/themes).

⁵ <https://www.iso.org/home.html>

⁶ <https://iec.ch/homepage>

D2.2 Standards and regulations analysis

ISO - 91.120.10 - Thermal insulation of buildings

Standards About us News Taking part Store

ISO

ICS > 91 > 91.120

91.120.10

THERMAL INSULATION OF BUILDINGS

INCLUDING ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF BUILDINGS

Energy efficiency in general, see [27.015](#)
Thermal insulation in general, see [27.220](#)
Thermal insulating materials, see [91.100.60](#)

Filter: Published standards Standards under development Withdrawn standards Projects deleted

STANDARD AND/OR PROJECT (72) ↓	STAGE	TC
ISO 6781-3:2015 Performance of buildings — Detection of heat, air and moisture irregularities in buildings by infrared methods — Part 3: Qualifications of equipment operators, data analysts and report writers	90.93	ISO/TC 163/SC 1
ISO 6781:1983 Thermal insulation — Qualitative detection of thermal irregularities in building envelopes — Infrared method	90.92	ISO/TC 163/SC 1
ISO 6946:2017 Building components and building elements — Thermal resistance and thermal transmittance — Calculation methods	60.60	ISO/TC 163/SC 2

Figure 3: Example of ISO standards

3 Regulations

This chapter provides an overview of the most relevant, current and upcoming regulations pertinent to the scope of AI4PublicPolicy.

The regulations considered touch upon three (3) main topics, namely, cybersecurity, data privacy & governance, and artificial intelligence. Although providing for an overview of other regulations would have been possible and, potentially, meaningful, for instance, by providing for the related national administrative laws, the selection presented in this Chapter is based on the considerations of the AI4PublicPolicy pilots' areas of activities with data, seen from a European (EU) perspective.

Note that, contrary to the general sense in which the term is used in this deliverable, in EU legal language, the term 'regulation', according to article 288 TFEU, refers to a specific source of secondary EU law. However, for consistency purposes of this deliverable with the 'Grant Agreement', this Chapter intends the term regulation in its generic meaning, and therefore it will include any relevant EU provision, being a Regulation, a Directive or merely a legislative proposal.

3.1 Cybersecurity Regulations

Table 1 - Directive (EU) 2016/1148

Name	Directive (EU) 2016/1148 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 July 2016 concerning measures for a high common level of security of network and information systems across the Union
Also known as	NIS Directive
When applicable	9 May 2018
Purpose	The NIS Directive was the first regulation to provide legal measures to increase the overall level of cybersecurity in the EU. The NIS directive will be reviewed soon, and s.
Scope	The NIS directive applies to operators of essential services and digital service providers. The directive lays down measures aimed at achieving a high level of security of network and information systems.
Key implications	The key implications are the implementation of risk management and reporting obligations for operators of essential services (including energy, transport, banking, financial market, health, drinking water and digital infrastructure) and digital service providers. Member States must ensure that digital service providers notify the competent authority without undue delay of any incident having a substantial impact on the provision of a service.
Stakeholders	European Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA), operators of essential services, digital service provider, DNS service provider.
Relevance for AI4PublicPolicy	In consideration of the national implementation of the NIS Directive, project pilots might be subject to take cybersecurity measures.
Link	http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2016/1148/oj

Table 2 - Update NIS Directive (NIS II)

Name	Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148
Also known as	NIS II
When applicable	Still in the legislative process.

Purpose	Strengthen the security requirements, address the security of supply chains, streamline reporting obligations, and introduce more stringent supervisory measures and stricter enforcement requirements, including harmonised sanctions across the EU.
Scope	NIS II broadens the scope of NIS I, to include providers of public electronic communications networks, wastewater and waste management, manufacturing of certain critical products, food, digital services such as social network and data centre services, space, postal services, public administration
Key implications	With the NIS II Directive, the Commission aims to adapt the previous NIS Directive in line with the changing technical and threat landscape and to make it more future proof. To this end, the NIS II Directive has expanded its scope and included more sectors and services that are either essential or important entities including public administration, providers of public electronic communications networks or services, digital services such as social media platforms, space and wastewater and waste management. Earlier distinction between operators of essential services and digital service providers has also been eliminated. Security requirements have also been further strengthened under the new Directive with a list of focused measures such as incident response and crisis management, cybersecurity testing, use of encryption and vulnerability handling and disclosure.
Stakeholders	European Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA), DNS service providers, TLD name registry, cloud computing service provider, data centre service provider, IXPs, DNSs, TLDs, social networking services platform, public administration entities.
Relevance for AI4PublicPolicy	Public administrations are explicitly mentioned in the scope of the revised Directive.
Link	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2020:823:FIN

Table 3 - Regulation 2019/881/EU

Name	Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/201
Also known as	The Cybersecurity Act
When applicable	27 June 2019
Purpose	To ensure an adequate level of cybersecurity by establishing a cybersecurity certification framework for digital products, services, and processes across the EU. To this end, the Cybersecurity Act lays out objectives, tasks and organisational matters for the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) and establishes governance and rules for certification of ICT products and services.
Scope	Applies EU-wide to ICT products, processes, and services, without prejudice to competences regarding activities concerning public security, defence, national security, and the activities of the State in areas of criminal law.

Key implications	The Cybersecurity Act introduces certification schemes for digital products, services, and processes. Each European scheme should specify: (a) the categories of products and services covered; (b) the cybersecurity requirements, such as standards or technical specifications; (c) the type of evaluation, such as self-assessment or third party; and (d) the intended level of assurance.
Relevance for AI4PublicPolicy	Equipment used for the project might be subject to cybersecurity certifications.
Link	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/881/oj

Table 4 - Regulation 910/2014/EU

Name	Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market and repealing Directive 1999/93/EC
Also known as	eIDAS
When applicable	September 2018
Purpose	To provide an advanced, harmonized legal framework for cross-border electronic identification, authentication, and website certification within the EU, to guarantee information security and to foster innovation.
Scope	Applies to electronic identification schemes notified by Member States, and trust service providers established in the Union.
Key implications	With the introduction of the eIDAS, qualified electronic signatures gain the same legal status as handwritten signatures; it stipulates that the legal effects and admissibility of digital signatures as evidence in legal proceedings should be recognised in all member states. However, each member state has the freedom to define the legal effects of the standard electronic signature. Furthermore, the eIDAS requires trust service providers to take appropriate technical and organisational measures to manage security risks for trust service providers.
Relevance for AI4PublicPolicy	It provides a framework for the legal recognition of citizens' (digital) identity and for sharing electronic documents from their European Digital Identity wallets.
Link	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2014/910/oj

3.2 Privacy & Governance

Table 5 - Regulation (EU) 2016/679

Name	Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC
Also known as	General Data Protection Regulation
When applicable	Since 25 May 2018
Purpose	To protect the fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons – specifically privacy or personal data protection.
Scope	Applies to the processing activities of personal data of citizens in the EU or by processors or controllers located in the EU. Personal data are data of an identified or identifiable natural person.

	Processing can include the collection, organization, structuring, sharing or erasure of data.
Key implications	Processing activities of personal data need a lawful basis, such as consent, performance of a contract, legitimate interest, vital interest, legal requirement, or public interest. Furthermore, the GDPR specifies the roles of entities involved in the data processing activities, such as the controller and the processor, and the corresponding responsibilities. The GDPR also provides rights to individuals whose personal data are processed. These rights include the right to transparency, the right of access to their personal data, the right to be forgotten, and the right to object to processing of personal data for certain purposes. Finally, the GDPR lays down six principles that are guiding in the EU data protection activities, namely (a) lawfulness, fairness and transparency; (b) purpose limitation; (c) data minimisation; (d) accuracy; (e) storage limitation; and (f) integrity and confidentiality.
Stakeholders	Data subjects, data controllers, data processors, data recipient, third parties under authority of controller or processor, enterprises, supervising authorities, international organisations.
Relevance for AI4PublicPolicy	The GDPR is relevant to AI4PublicPolicy due to the scope of the piloting activities ⁷ .
Link	http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj

Table 6 - Directive 2002/58/EC

Name	Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (Directive on privacy and electronic communications)
Also known as	ePrivacy Directive
When applicable	12 July 2002
Purpose	To protect privacy of EU citizens, and the confidentiality of tracking and monitoring practices. To ensure alignment with the GDPR, the ePrivacy Directive is currently being updated into the ePrivacy <i>Regulation</i> .
Scope	Applies to the processing of personal data related to the publicly available electronic communications sector, such as the internet or mobile phone networks, and is thus sector specific.
Key implications	Given that it is a directive, the requirements for protecting privacy have been implemented into national laws or regulations. The ePrivacy Directive will, among other things, address confidentiality of communication between machines (Internet of Things) or individuals on publicly accessible networks.
Stakeholders	Users, subscribers, service providers.
Relevance for AI4PublicPolicy	Complementing the GDPR, the ePrivacy Directive establishes rules for the digital communication services, such as web sites and apps, developed in the project.
Link	http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2002/58/oj

⁷ More detailed information in this respect is provided in the related deliverables under Work Package 9 on Ethics Requirements.

Table 7 - COM/2017/010

Name	Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL concerning the respect for private life and the protection of personal data in electronic communications and repealing Directive 2002/58/EC
Also known as	ePrivacy Regulation
When applicable	Still in the legislative process
Purpose	To update the 2002 ePrivacy Directive to be more align with the GDPR.
Scope	The ePrivacy Regulation widens the scope of the directive.
Key implications	As the ePrivacy Directive becomes the ePrivacy Regulation, it will become self-executing and legally binding in EU countries. The privacy rules apply to communication services, such as WhatsApp and Skype, and to new forms of electronic communications such as IoT. Compared to the Directive, the rules are tightened. Key implications are to the regulation of metadata and streamlining cookies provision. Consent will no longer be required for non-privacy intrusive cookies.
Stakeholders	Interpersonal and electronic communication services, end-users
Relevance for AI4PublicPolicy	Complementing the GDPR, the ePrivacy framework establishes rules for the digital communication services, such as web sites and apps, developed in the project.
Link	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52017PC0010

Table 8 - Open Data Directive

Name	Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information
Also known as	Open Data Directive
When applicable	20 June 2019, subject Member State implementation by 17 July 2021.
Purpose	Promote the use and re-use of open data held by public bodies.
Scope	this Directive establishes a set of minimum rules governing the re-use and the practical arrangements for facilitating the re-use of existing documents held by public sector bodies of the Member States; existing documents held by certain public undertakings as defined by the law; research data pursuant to the conditions established by the law.
Key implications	Member States shall ensure that documents to which this Directive applies shall be re-usable for commercial or non-commercial purposes.
Stakeholders	Public bodies, citizens and other undertakings
Relevance for AI4PublicPolicy	Pilots leaders might be subject to certain data/document accessing obligations.
Link	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32019L1024

Table 9 - EC Proposal for a Regulation on European data governance (Data Governance Act)

Name	Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on European data governance
Also known as	Data Governance Act
When applicable	Still in the legislative process.
Purpose	To increase trust in data intermediaries and to strengthen data-sharing mechanisms across the EU. The DGA responds to the issue of lack of availability of data for research and innovation.
Scope	Reuse of certain public sector data, data intermediaries and data sharing framework.
Key implications	Introduction of mechanisms for the re-use of data produced by the public sector, creation of data intermediaries, and the establishment of the European Data Innovation Board.
Stakeholders	Data holders, data users, public sector bodies, bodies governed by public law.
Relevance for AI4PublicPolicy	Pilot leaders might be subject to or voluntarily undertake data sharing pursuant to the framework established in the DGA.
Link	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020PC0767

3.3 Artificial Intelligence

Table 10 - COM (2021) 206 Proposal for Artificial Intelligence Act

Name	COM (2021) 206: Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Laying Down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence ('Artificial Intelligence Act') and Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts.
Also known as	Artificial Intelligence Act
When applicable	Still in the legislative process.
Purpose	To encourage the development, deployment and use of secure, trustworthy and human-centric artificial intelligence.
Scope	Applies to placing on the market and putting into service of AI systems
Key implications	AI systems are divided into four risks levels. Depending on the risk level, they are subject to transparency requirements, data quality, documentation and cybersecurity requirements, or fully prohibited.
Stakeholders	Providers, users, authorized representatives, importers, distributors, operators market surveillance authorities, national supervisory authority, national competent authority.
Relevance for AI4PublicPolicy	As AI4PublicPolicy is developing AI-systems that may have an impact on individuals. The proposed AI Act provides for a regulatory framework on risk assessment and mitigation of the potential risks incurred.
Link	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52021PC0206

4 Standards

To identify applicable standards to the AI4PublicPolicy pilots, an analysis was done on the use cases defined in D2.1, which resulted in a definition of interesting categories within the scope of the project. The list was refined after the standard identification work, being the final list of categories:

- General Standards
- Data Standards
- Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility
- Citizens and Business Services Optimization
- Noise Management
- Energy Management
- Water Infrastructure planning and maintenance

In the sections below are presented the standards, divided by the categories mentioned above. In the reference tables, they have the following fields:

- Standard: standard nomenclature
- Focus: how the standard is classified
- Domain: the area/sub-section of the standard's category
- Brief Description: as indicated, brief description of the standard
- Link: standard hyperlink

In total we identified 63 different standards, which are presented in the collection of tables below. It is important to mention that all these identified standards are applicable to the AI4PublicPolicy pilots, but it's use is not mandatory.

4.1 General Standards

Table 11 - ISO 9001:2015

Standard	ISO 9001:2015
Focus	Quality management systems
Domain	Requirements
Brief Description	ISO 9001:2015 specifies requirements for a quality management system
Link	Link

Table 12 - ISO 9004:2018

Standard	ISO 9004:2018
Focus	Quality management
Domain	Quality of an organization — Guidance to achieve sustained success
Brief Description	ISO 9004:2018 gives guidelines for enhancing an organization's ability to achieve sustained success.
Link	Link

Table 13 - ISO/IEC 27001

Standard	ISO/IEC 27001
Focus	Information technology
Domain	Security techniques — Information security management systems — Requirements
Brief Description	ISO/IEC 27001:2013 specifies the requirements for establishing, implementing, maintaining and continually improving an

	information security management system within the context of the organization
Link	Link

Table 14 - ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018

Standard	ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018
Focus	Information technology
Domain	Service management — Part 1: Service management system requirements
Brief Description	It specifies requirements for an organization to establish, implement, maintain and continually improve a service management system (SMS). The requirements specified in this document include the planning, design, transition, delivery and improvement of services to meet the service requirements and deliver value.
Link	Link

Table 15 - ISO 14001:2015

Standard	ISO 14001:2015
Focus	Environmental management systems
Domain	Requirements with guidance for use
Brief Description	ISO 14001:2015 specifies the requirements for an environmental management system that an organization can use to enhance its environmental performance
Link	Link

Table 16 - ISO 55001:2014

Standard	ISO 55001:2014
Focus	Asset management
Domain	Management systems — Requirements
Brief Description	ISO 55001:2014 specifies requirements for an asset management system within the context of the organization. It defines a set of requirements that, when implemented and maintained, ensure the good performance of an organization's asset management, meeting the needs and expectations of stakeholders or interested parties and guaranteeing the creation and maintenance of value.
Link	Link

Table 17 - ISO 45001:2019

Standard	ISO 45001:2019
Focus	Occupational health and safety management systems
Domain	Requirements with guidance for use
Brief Description	ISO 45001:2018 specifies requirements for an occupational health and safety (OH&S) management system, and gives guidance for its use, to enable organizations to provide safe and healthy workplaces by preventing work-related injury and ill health, as well as by proactively improving its OH&S performance.
Link	Link

Table 18 - ISO 50001:2018

Standard	ISO 50001:2018
Focus	Energy management systems
Domain	Requirements with guidance for use
Brief Description	It specifies requirements for establishing, implementing, maintaining and improving an energy management system (EnMS). The intended outcome is to enable an organization to follow a systematic approach in achieving continual improvement of energy performance and the EnMS.
Link	Link

Table 19 - ISO/IEC TR 24372:2021

Standard	ISO/IEC TR 24372:2021
Focus	Information technology
Domain	Artificial intelligence (AI) — Overview of computational approaches for AI systems
Brief Description	This document provides an overview of the state of the art of computational approaches for AI systems, by describing: a) main computational characteristics of AI systems; b) main algorithms and approaches used in AI systems
Link	Link

Table 20 - WCAG 2.0

Standard	WCAG 2.0
Focus	Web Content
Domain	Web Accessibility Guidelines
Brief Description	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.0 covers a wide range of recommendations for making Web content more accessible. Following these guidelines will make content accessible to a wider range of people with disabilities, including blindness and low vision, deafness and hearing loss, learning disabilities, cognitive limitations, limited movement, speech disabilities, photosensitivity and combinations of these. Following these guidelines will also often make your Web content more usable to users in general.
Link	Link

Table 21 - OAuth 2.0

Standard	OAuth 2.0
Focus	Authorization
Domain	industry-standard protocol
Brief Description	OAuth 2.0 focuses on client developer simplicity while providing specific authorization flows for web applications, desktop applications, mobile phones, and living room devices. This specification and its extensions are being developed within the IETF OAuth Working Group.
Link	Link

Table 22 - Distributed Network Protocol 3

Standard	Distributed Network Protocol 3
Focus	Communications protocols
Domain	Communications protocols
Brief Description	It is a set of communications protocols used between components in process automation systems. Its main use is in utilities such as electric and water companies
Link	Link

4.2 Data Standards

Table 23 - ISO/IEC 11179:2015

Standard	ISO/IEC 11179:2015
Focus	Information technology
Domain	Metadata registries (MDR)
Brief Description	It provides the means for understanding and associating the individual parts of ISO/IEC 11179 and is the foundation for a conceptual understanding of metadata and metadata registries. It is applicable to the formulation of data representations, concepts, meanings and relationships to be shared among people and machines, independent of the organization that produces the data. It is not applicable to the physical representation of data as bits and bytes at the machine level.
Link	Link

Table 24 - ISO/IEC TR 19583:2019

Standard	ISO/IEC TR 19583:2019
Focus	Information technology
Domain	Concepts and usage of metadata
Brief Description	It describes the basic concept of metadata, and its relationship to both data and metamodels.
Link	Link

Table 25 - ISO 19118:2011

Standard	ISO 19118:2011
Focus	Geographic information
Domain	Encoding
Brief Description	specifies the requirements for defining encoding rules for use for the interchange of data that conform to the geographic information in the set of International Standards known as the "ISO 19100 series", including requirements for creating encoding rules based on UML schemas, requirements for creating encoding services, and requirements for XML-based encoding rules for neutral interchange of data.

Link	Link
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Table 26 - ISO/IEC 21778:2017

Standard	ISO/IEC 21778:2017
Focus	Information technology
Domain	The JSON data interchange syntax
Brief Description	The goal of ISO/IEC 21778:2017 is to define the syntax of valid JSON texts.
Link	Link

Table 27 - ISO 19111:2019

Standard	ISO 19111:2019
Focus	Geographic information
Domain	Referencing by coordinates
Brief Description	It defines the conceptual schema for the description of referencing by coordinates. It describes the minimum data required to define coordinate reference systems.
Link	Link

Table 28 - ISO 19112:2019

Standard	ISO 19112:2019
Focus	Geographic information
Domain	Spatial referencing by geographic identifiers
Brief Description	It defines the conceptual schema for the description of referencing by coordinates. It describes the minimum data required to define coordinate reference systems.
Link	Link

Table 29 - ISO 19128:2005

Standard	ISO 19128:2005
Focus	Geographic information
Domain	Web map server interface
Brief Description	specifies the behaviour of a service that produces spatially referenced maps dynamically from geographic information.
Link	Link

4.3 Parking Space Management and Urban Mobility

Table 30 - ISO/TR 4445:2021

Standard	ISO/TR 4445:2021
Focus	Intelligent transport systems

Domain	Mobility integration — Role model of ITS service application in smart cities
Brief Description	It describes a basic role model of smart city intelligent transport systems (ITS) service applications as a common platform for smart city instantiation, directly communicating via secure ITS interfaces.
Link	Link

4.4 Citizens and Business Services Optimization

Table 31 - ISO 19011:2018

Standard	ISO 19011:2018
Focus	Auditing management systems
Domain	Guidelines for auditing management systems
Brief Description	It provides guidance on auditing management systems, including the principles of auditing, managing an audit programme and conducting management system audits, as well as guidance on the evaluation of competence of individuals involved in the audit process. These activities include the individual(s) managing the audit programme, auditors and audit teams.
Link	Link

4.5 Noise Management

Table 32 - ISO 1996-1:2016

Standard	ISO 1996-1:2016
Focus	Acoustics
Domain	Description, measurement and assessment of environmental noise - Part 1 : Basic quantities and assessment procedures
Brief Description	ISO 1996-1:2016 defines the basic quantities to be used for the description of noise in community environments and describes basic assessment procedures. It also specifies methods to assess environmental noise and gives guidance on predicting the potential annoyance response of a community to long-term exposure from various types of environmental noises
Link	Link

Table 33 - ISO 1996-2:2017

Standard	ISO 1996-2:2017
Focus	Acoustics
Domain	Description, measurement and assessment of environmental noise - Part 2: Determination of sound pressure levels
Brief Description	ISO 1996-2:2017 describes how sound pressure levels intended as a basis for assessing environmental noise limits or comparison of scenarios in spatial studies can be determined
Link	Link

Table 34 - ISO 1999:2013

Standard	ISO 1999:2013
Focus	Acoustics
Domain	Estimation of noise-induced hearing loss

Brief Description	ISO 1999:2013 specifies a method for calculating the expected noise-induced permanent threshold shift in the hearing threshold levels of adult populations due to various levels and durations of noise exposure;
Link	Link

Table 35 - ISO 7029:2017

Standard	ISO 7029:2017
Focus	Acoustics
Domain	Statistical distribution of hearing thresholds related to age and gender
Brief Description	ISO 7029:2017 provides descriptive statistics of the hearing threshold deviation for populations of ontologically normal persons of various ages under monaural earphone listening conditions. It specifies the following, for populations within the age limits from 18 years to 80 years for the range of audiometric frequencies from 125 Hz to 8 000 Hz.
Link	Link

Table 36 - ISO 9612:2009

Standard	ISO 9612:2009
Focus	Acoustics
Domain	Determination of occupational noise exposure — Engineering method
Brief Description	ISO 9612:2009 specifies an engineering method for measuring workers' exposure to noise in a working environment and calculating the noise exposure level.
Link	Link

Table 37 - ISO 14257:2001

Standard	ISO 14257:2001
Focus	Acoustics
Domain	Measurement and parametric description
Brief Description	Measurement and parametric description of spatial sound distribution curves in workrooms for evaluation of their acoustical performance
Link	Link

Table 38 - IEC 61672

Standard	IEC 61672
Focus	Electroacoustics
Domain	Sound level meters - Part 1: Specifications
Brief Description	IEC 61672-1:2013 gives electro acoustical performance specifications for three kinds of sound measuring instruments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • time-weighting sound level meters that measure exponential-time-weighted, frequency-weighted sound levels; • integrating-averaging sound level meters that measure time-averaged, frequency-weighted sound levels; and • integrating sound level meters that measure frequency-weighted sound exposure levels.

Link	Link
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Table 39 - BS 4142

Standard	BS 4142
Focus	Acoustics
Domain	Methods for rating and assessing industrial and commercial sound
Brief Description	<p>It provides methods for rating and assessing sound of an industrial and/or commercial nature, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sound from industrial and manufacturing processes • Sound from fixed installations of mechanical and electrical plant and equipment; this commonly includes air conditioning units and extractions systems • Sound from the loading and unloading of goods and materials at industrial and/or commercial premises <p>Sound from mobile plant and vehicles that is an intrinsic part of the overall sound emanating from premises or processes, such as that from forklift trucks, or that from train or ship movements on or around an industrial and/or commercial site.</p>
Link	Link

4.6 Energy Management

Table 40 - IEC 61724-1:2021

Standard	IEC 61724-1:2021
Focus	Photovoltaic system performance
Domain	Photovoltaic system performance - Part 1: Monitoring
Brief Description	IEC 61724-1:2021 outlines terminology, equipment, and methods for performance monitoring and analysis of photovoltaic (PV) systems
Link	Link

Table 41 - IEC TS 61724-2:2016

Standard	IEC TS 61724-2:2016
Focus	Photovoltaic system performance
Domain	Photovoltaic system performance - Part 2: Capacity evaluation method
Brief Description	IEC TS 61724-2:2016(E) defines a procedure for measuring and analyzing the power production of a specific photovoltaic system with the goal of evaluating the quality of the PV system performance. The test is intended to be applied during a relatively short time period (a few relatively sunny days). The intent of this document is to specify a framework procedure for comparing the measured power produced against the expected power from a PV system on relatively sunny days.
Link	Link

Table 42 - IEC TS 61724-3:2016

Standard	IEC TS 61724-3:2016
Focus	Photovoltaic system performance
Domain	Photovoltaic system performance - Part 3: Energy evaluation method

Brief Description	IEC TS 61724-3:2016(E) defines a procedure for measuring and analyzing the energy production of a specific photovoltaic system relative to expected electrical energy production for the same system from actual weather conditions as defined by the stakeholders of the test.
Link	Link

Table 43 - ISO 7345:2018

Standard	ISO 7345:2018
Focus	Thermal performance of buildings and building components
Domain	Physical quantities and definitions
Brief Description	ISO 7345:2018 defines physical quantities used in the thermal performance of buildings and building elements and gives the corresponding symbols and units.
Link	Link

Table 44 - ISO 9869-1:2014

Standard	ISO 9869-1:2014
Focus	Thermal insulation — Building elements
Domain	In-situ measurement of thermal resistance and thermal transmittance — Part 1: Heat flow meter method
Brief Description	ISO 9869-1:2014 describes the heat flow meter method for the measurement of the thermal transmission properties of plane building components, primarily consisting of opaque layers perpendicular to the heat flow and having no significant lateral heat flow.
Link	Link

Table 45 - ISO 52010-1:2017

Standard	ISO 52010-1:2017
Focus	Energy performance of buildings — External climatic conditions
Domain	Part 1: Conversion of climatic data for energy calculations
Brief Description	The main element in ISO 52010-1:2017 is the calculation of solar irradiance on a surface with arbitrary orientation and tilt. A simple method for conversion of solar irradiance to illuminance is also provided. The solar irradiance and illuminance on an arbitrary surface are applicable as input for energy and daylighting calculations, for building elements (such as roofs, facades and windows) and for components of technical building systems (such as thermal solar collectors, PV panels).
Link	Link

Table 46 - RESET® Air

Standard	RESET® Air
Focus	Air quality
Domain	Air quality monitoring
Brief Description	RESET Air is designed to prioritize on-going results and long-term occupant health with a focus on the operational phase of the built environment. In the case of RESET Air, indoor air quality data is required to be continuously gathered through air quality monitors

	Note: The RESET Standard consists of five stand-alone standards: Materials, Air, Water, Energy, and Circularity. All stand-alone Standards (except RESET® Air) has the official release beginning of 2022
Link	Link

Table 47 - ISO 4225:2020

Standard	ISO 4225:2020
Focus	Air quality
Domain	General aspects — Vocabulary
Brief Description	It specifies terms and definitions that are related to air quality.
Link	Link

Table 48 - ISO 4226:2007

Standard	ISO 4226:2007
Focus	Air quality
Domain	General aspects — Units of measurement
Brief Description	ISO 4226:2008 lays down the units to be used when reporting results of air quality measurements.
Link	Link

Table 49 - ISO 7168-1:1999

Standard	ISO 7168-1:1999
Focus	Air quality
Domain	Exchange of data — Part 1: General data format
Brief Description	ISO 7168-1 specifies the general data format for the exchange of air quality data. This general data format supports both the direct readability and the automated processing of data files. Each information presented in a data file prepared in accordance with ISO 7168-1 is related to a defined keyword and therefore consistently self-explanatory. The general data format is intended for the international exchange of air quality data.
Link	Link

Table 50 - ISO 7168-2:1999

Standard	ISO 7168-2:1999
Focus	Air quality
Domain	Exchange of data — Part 2: Condensed data format
Brief Description	ISO 7168-2 specifies a condensed data format which is intended only for the exchange of data files between automatic data processing systems. A good knowledge of the file structure is necessary for the interpretation of these data files.
Link	Link

Table 51 - ISO 7708:1995

Standard	ISO 7708:1995
Focus	Air quality
Domain	Particle size fraction definitions for health-related sampling

Brief Description	Describes procedures for adjusting air quality measurements for changes in temperature, pressure and humidity during the sampling period
Link	Link

Table 52 - ISO 8756:1994

Standard	ISO 8756:1994
Focus	Air quality
Domain	Handling of temperature, pressure and humidity data
Brief Description	Describes procedures for adjusting air quality measurements for changes in temperature, pressure and humidity during the sampling period
Link	Link

Table 53 - ISO 9169:2006

Standard	ISO 9169:2006
Focus	Air quality
Domain	Definition and determination of performance characteristics of an automatic measuring system
Brief Description	ISO 9169:2006 provides definitions and specifies methods to determine performance characteristics of an identified automatic air quality measuring system.
Link	Link

Table 54 - ISO 14064-2:2019

Standard	ISO 14064-2:2019
Focus	Greenhouse gases
Domain	Part 2: Specification with guidance at the project level for quantification, monitoring and reporting of greenhouse gas emission reductions or removal enhancements
Brief Description	It specifies principles and requirements and provides guidance at the project level for the quantification, monitoring and reporting of activities intended to cause greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reductions or removal enhancements
Link	Link

Table 55 - ISO 18523-2:2018

Standard	ISO 18523-2:2018
Focus	Energy performance of buildings
Domain	Schedule and condition of building, zone and space usage for energy calculation — Part 2: Residential buildings
Brief Description	ISO 18523-2:2018 specifies the formats to present the schedule and conditions of zone and space usage (referred to as input data of energy calculations) for residential buildings.
Link	Link

Table 56 - ISO 10077-1:2017

Standard	ISO 10077-1:2017
Focus	Thermal performance of windows, doors and shutters
Domain	Calculation of thermal transmittance — Part 1: General

Brief Description	ISO 10077-1:2017 specifies methods for the calculation of the thermal transmittance of windows and pedestrian doors consisting of glazed and/or opaque panels fitted in a frame, with and without shutters.
Link	Link

Table 57 - ISO 12655:2013

Standard	ISO 12655:2013
Focus	Energy performance of buildings
Domain	Presentation of measured energy use of buildings
Brief Description	ISO 12655:2013 sets out a consistent methodology to present energy use in buildings, which is specified clearly with the energy usage, corresponding boundary and the energy data (presented with original energy carriers or equivalent energy). ISO 12655:2013 is applicable to the presentation of energy use of civil buildings for data collection, metering, statistics, audit and analysis.
Link	Link

Table 58 - ISO 52000-1:2017

Standard	ISO 52000-1:2017
Focus	Energy performance of buildings
Domain	Overarching EPB assessment — Part 1: General framework and procedures
Brief Description	ISO 52000-1:2017 establishes a systematic, comprehensive and modular structure for assessing the energy performance of new and existing buildings (EPB) in a holistic way. It is applicable to the assessment of overall energy use of a building, by measurement or calculation, and the calculation of energy performance in terms of primary energy or other energy-related metrics. It takes into account the specific possibilities and limitations for the different applications, such as building design, new buildings 'as built', and existing buildings in the use phase as well as renovation.
Link	Link

Table 59 - ISO 52003-1:2017

Standard	ISO 52003-1:2017
Focus	Energy performance of buildings
Domain	Indicators, requirements, ratings and certificates — Part 1: General aspects and application to the overall energy performance
Brief Description	ISO 52003-1:2017 describes the relation between the EPB indicators and the EPB requirements and EPB ratings, and it discusses the importance of project-specific, tailored values as requirement or reference for certain EPB indicators. ISO 52003-1:2017 also includes a couple of possible EPB labels and it lists the different steps to be taken when establishing an EPB certification scheme.
Link	Link

Table 60 - ISO 52016-1:2017

Standard	ISO 52016-1:2017
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Focus	Energy performance of buildings
Domain	Energy needs for heating and cooling, internal temperatures and sensible and latent heat loads — Part 1: Calculation procedures
Brief Description	ISO 52016-1:2017 specifies calculation methods for the assessment
Link	Link

Table 61 - ISO 52017-1:2017

Standard	ISO 52017-1:2017
Focus	Energy performance of buildings
Domain	Sensible and latent heat loads and internal temperatures — Part 1: Generic calculation procedures
Brief Description	Specific calculation procedures based on the generic calculation procedures of ISO 52017-1:2017 are given in ISO 52016-1. The specific simplifications, assumptions and boundary conditions in ISO 52016-1 are tailored to the respective application areas, such as the energy need for heating and cooling and for humidification and dehumidification, hourly internal temperature, design heating and cooling and humidification and dehumidification load.
Link	Link

Table 62 - ISO 52018-1:2017

Standard	ISO 52018-1:2017
Focus	Energy performance of buildings
Domain	Indicators for partial EPB requirements related to thermal energy balance and fabric features — Part 1: Overview of options
Brief Description	The set of EPB assessment standards produces a great number of overall and partial EPB indicators as outputs, which can be used for different purposes. ISO 52018-1:2017 deals with the use as requirement of partial EPB indicators related to the fabric and related to the thermal balance of the building. Thermal balance aspects concern both the heating and cooling needs and the free floating temperatures, especially with respect to overheating or too cold indoor temperatures. ISO 52018-1:2017 can support both private parties and public regulators (and all stakeholders involved in the regulatory process) with the "post-processing" of these outputs.
Link	Link

Table 63 - ISO 15099:2003

Standard	ISO 15099:2003
Focus	Thermal performance of windows, doors and shading devices
Domain	Detailed calculations
Brief Description	It specifies detailed calculation procedures for determining the thermal and optical transmission properties (e.g., thermal transmittance, total solar energy transmittance) of window and door systems based on the most up-to-date algorithms and methods, and the relevant solar and thermal properties of all components.
Link	Link

4.7 Water Infrastructure planning and maintenance

Table 64 - ISO 24510:2007

Standard	ISO 24510:2007
Focus	Activities relating to drinking water and wastewater services
Domain	Guidelines for the assessment and for the improvement of the service to users
Brief Description	ISO 24510:2007 specifies the elements of drinking water and wastewater services of relevance and interest to users. It also provides guidance on how to identify users' needs and expectations and how to assess whether they are being met.
Link	Link

Table 65 - ISO 24512:2007

Standard	ISO 24512:2007
Focus	Activities relating to drinking water and wastewater services
Domain	Guidelines for the management of drinking water utilities and for the assessment of drinking water services
Brief Description	ISO 24512:2007 provides guidelines for the management of drinking water utilities and for the assessment of drinking water services. ISO 24512:2007 addresses drinking water systems in their entirety and is applicable to systems at any level of development (e.g. on-site systems, distribution networks, treatment facilities).
Link	Link

Table 66 - ISO 24516-1:2016

Standard	ISO 24516-1:2016
Focus	Guidelines for the management of assets of water supply and wastewater systems
Domain	Part 1: Drinking water distribution networks
Brief Description	ISO 24516-1:2016 specifies guidelines for technical aspects, tools and good practices for the management of assets of drinking water networks to maintain value from existing assets.
Link	Link

Table 67 - ISO/TS 24522:2019

Standard	ISO/TS 24522:2019
Focus	Event detection process
Domain	Guidelines for water and wastewater utilities
Brief Description	It provides guidance for water utilities on the detection and classification of water and wastewater events.
Link	Link

Table 68 - ISO 24518:2015

Standard	ISO 24518:2015
Focus	Activities relating to drinking water and wastewater services
Domain	Crisis management of water utilities
Brief Description	ISO 24518:2015 provides general guidance to water utilities to develop and implement a crisis management system.
Link	Link

Table 69 - ISO/TS 24520:2017

Standard	ISO/TS 24520:2017
Focus	Service activities relating to drinking water supply systems and wastewater systems
Domain	Crisis management — Good practice for technical aspects
Brief Description	ISO/TS 24520:2017 provides guidance to water utilities on good practice in technical aspects of crisis management. ISO/TS 24520:2017 is applicable to all water utilities, of whatever size, whether public or private, that wish to review the effectiveness and efficiency of their service activities relating to preparation for, response to and recovery from a crisis.
Link	Link

Table 70 - ISO/TS 24541:2020

Standard	ISO/TS 24541:2020
Focus	Service activities relating to drinking water supply, wastewater and stormwater systems
Domain	Guidelines for the implementation of continuous monitoring systems for drinking water quality and operational parameters in drinking water distribution networks
Brief Description	It specifies guidelines for the implementation of continuous monitoring systems for drinking water quality and operational parameters in drinking water distribution networks.
Link	Link

Table 71 - ISO 46001:2019

Standard	ISO 46001:2019
Focus	Water efficiency management systems
Domain	Requirements with guidance for use
Brief Description	This document specifies requirements and contains guidance for its use in establishing, implementing and maintaining a water efficiency management system. It is applicable to organizations of all types and sizes that use water. It is focused on end-use consumers.
Link	Link

Table 72 - ISO 21053:2019

Standard	ISO 21053:2019
Focus	LCA and recycling of ductile iron pipes for water applications
Domain	Life cycle analysis and recycling of ductile iron pipes for water applications
Brief Description	It specifies the evaluation method of life cycle analysis of ductile iron pipes used for water applications. Studies on economic and environmental impacts are important for utility decision-makers as they seek to balance budget concerns over immediate and long-term needs across acquisition, operations and maintenance, and planned end of life. For authorities and engineers designing pipeline systems, the life cycle cost analysis serves as a tool to study various scenarios to determine the right solution for site-specific conditions and community values, as well as to provide the necessary data to support those decisions.

Link	Link
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Table 73 - ISO/TR 3313:2018

Standard	ISO/TR 3313:2018
Focus	Measurement of fluid flow in closed conduits
Domain	Guidelines on the effects of flow pulsations on flow-measurement instruments
Brief Description	ISO/TR 3313:2018 defines pulsating flow, compares it with steady flow, indicates how it can be detected, and describes the effects it has on orifice plates, nozzles or Venturi tubes, turbine and vortex flowmeters when these devices are being used to measure fluid flow in a pipe.
Link	Link

5 Conclusions

This document aims to bring together a set of Standards and Regulations that may be applicable to AI4PublicPolicy’s pilots. This list is just a suggestion that the pilots may or may not implement or may have already implemented.

The chart below represents all the 63 Standards listed in the document, with the total number for each category.

Figure 4: Standards Chart

The legal discussion captured in this document focused on a selection of the most relevant regulations horizontally pertinent to all pilots in relation to the three (3) thematic areas, namely, cybersecurity, data privacy and governance as well as artificial intelligence. Sector specific regulations relating to the scope of a single pilot were, therefore, not addressed in this document, but it is intended that they are to an extent considered under Task 1.5 “Ethical and Legal Analysis”⁸. Further, the discussion surfaced that the European Regulator has taken legislative initiatives in the fields of cybersecurity, data, and AI, this has, already resulted, or is about to result, in the harmonization of the applicable laws across Member States, also, known, as ‘Europeanisation’.

The chart below represents all the Regulations listed in the document, with the total number for each category.

⁸ For instance, the Payment Services Directive is relevant for Athens Pilot, due to the parking payments conducted through the application wallet functionality.

D2.2 Standards and regulations analysis

Figure 5: Regulations Chart

The work carried out in this Task (Task 2.2 - Analysis of Applicable Standards and Regulations) will be continued in WP8, namely in Task 8.3 (T8.3 - Standardization and Policy Making Activities).